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Heavy flavor production at the LHC

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Abstract

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This letter presents the latest results on heavy flavour production at the LHC in pp, p-Pb and Pb-Pb collisions and how the different measurement allows us to probe the QGP and learn more about heavy flavour formations

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The measurement of the production of heavy flavor hadrons, which contain one charm or beauty quark, is a very powerful tool to investigate the properties of the quark-gluon plasma (QGP). Indeed, because of their large masses ($m_b > m_c \gg \Lambda_{QCD}$), they have a very short formation time and can only be produced at the initial hard scatterings of a collision and therefore experience the entire medium evolution. Measurement of heavy flavor production in high energy Pb–Pb collisions, like the ones performed at the LHC, allows to explore QGP properties via the way the medium affects the heavy flavor formation. In addition, measurements in p–Pb collisions help to disentangle between final state and initial state effects, as well as testing the interplay between soft and hard processes. Finally, measurement in proton-proton collisions serve as reference to p–Pb and Pb–Pb measurements, as well as a test of perturbative QCD models regarding hadron formation. In this letter, some of the latest results measured by ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb regarding heavy-flavor production are presented.

In Figure 1 left, the forward to backward production ratio R_{FB} of the D^0 is presented, measured by LHCb [1] in p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 8.16$ and 5.02 TeV as a function of transverse momentum. This result shows a significant asymmetry at low p_T , and a rising trend with increasing p_T beyond 5 GeV/c. The result is also higher at high p_T than the prediction of nPDF calculations [2, 3, 4].

Figure 1: Left : D^0 forward to backward production ratio as a function of p_T measured by LHCb [1] compared with models [2, 3, 4]. Right : Λ_c^+ R_{pPb} in p–Pb collisions and R_{AA} in Pb–Pb collisions measured by ALICE [5] compared with nPDF calculations [2, 3].

In Figure 1 right, the R_{pPb} of the Λ_c^+ measured by ALICE in p–Pb collisions [5] at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV is presented, compared with the R_{AA} in central and semi-central Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV. It is also compared with the corresponding R_{AA} of the D^0 meson and with nPDFs calculations [2, 3]. The Λ_c^+ R_{pPb} and the R_{AA} in central collisions are below 1, although the former is closer to unity than the latter, which is expected because the shadowing, which causes a suppression in the production, is smaller in p–Pb compared to Pb–Pb collisions. It is also notable that the Λ_c^+ and D^0 values are very similar to each other, which indicates that there is no significant enhancement of charm baryons compared to charm mesons in p–Pb and Pb–Pb versus pp.

The difference in behavior between charm baryons and mesons can be explored further by looking at the Λ_c^+/D^0 ratio, which is presented in Figure 2. The ratio measured by CMS [6] in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 5.02$ TeV and Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV is compared with the ALICE measurement [5] in pp and p–Pb collisions at the same center-of-mass collision energy, compared with models [7, 8,

9, 10, 11]. All models, despite using completely different theoretical frameworks, successfully describe the ratio in pp collisions both for ALICE at low p_T and CMS at high p_T . When comparing the values in pp and p–Pb collisions, one can observe that the ratios are compatible at low p_T , and the shift of the maximum of the ratio towards higher p_T in p–Pb collisions can be explained by the radial flow. The ratio in Pb–Pb collisions is compatible at high p_T with the pp values, which indicates there is no significant contribution from the coalescence process at high p_T .

Figure 2: Λ_c^+/D^0 ratio as in function of p_T in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 5$ TeV (top) measured by ALICE [5] (left) and CMS [6] (right) compared with models [7, 8, 9, 10, 11], and with the ratio in p–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5$ TeV measured by ALICE (bottom left) and in Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV measured by CMS (bottom right).

In Figure 3 the R_{AA} of the prompt D mesons as a function of p_T measured by ALICE [12] is presented in central Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV, compared with the R_{AA} of other particles. It shows a mass ordering at low p_T , where the lighter particles are more suppressed than the heavier one. In the 10–20 GeV/c region, the R_{AA} of the prompt D mesons is similar the R_{AA} of the prompt J/ψ , but smaller the R_{AA} of the non-prompt J/ψ , coming from the decay of B mesons. This indicates that the charm quarks lose more energy in the medium than the beauty quarks. Figure 3 also shows the R_{AA} and elliptic flow v_2 of the prompt D mesons as a function of p_T for semi-central collisions. The values are compared with several model calculations [8, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20]. These models struggle to provide a good description for both the nuclear modification factor and the elliptic flow together: models that are able to reproduce the p_T trend of the R_{AA} tend to underestimate the v_2 , and on the other hand models that are compatible with the v_2 values in the whole p_T range tend to miss the R_{AA} values at low p_T . This shows that the understanding of the in-medium behavior of the charm quarks is not complete yet. However, it is still possible to extract from the model comparison some constraints on the charm quark spatial diffusion coefficient: $1.5 < 2\pi D_s T_c < 4.5$ for a transition temperature $T_c \approx 155$ MeV.

In Figure 4 left, the non-prompt to prompt R_{AA} ratio for D^0 mesons is shown measured by ALICE [25] in central Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV. For $p_T >$

Figure 3: D meson R_{AA} as a function of p_T measured by ALICE [12] compared with other species (left) and with models [8, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20] (middle), and D meson v_2 (right) as a function of p_T compared with models.

69 5 GeV/c, the ratio is larger than unity, indicating a larger suppression of the prompt
 70 D^0 mesons. The values are also compared with model predictions [26, 19, 18, 27].
 71 These models, whether they include inelastic collisions only [26] or both radiative and
 72 collisional processes [19, 18] show a similar trend at low p_T . The minimum can be
 73 explained with coalescence: prompt D^0 acquire a higher momentum than the parent
 74 charm quark, leading to a hardening of the p_T spectra. Models also show that the
 75 energy loss in the medium is dependent on the mass of the quark, the lighter charm
 76 quark losing more energy than the beauty quark which leads the prompt mesons
 77 being more suppressed than the non-prompt mesons.

Figure 4: Left : ratio of the non-prompt and prompt D^0 R_{AA} as a function of p_T measured by ALICE [25] compared with models [26, 19, 18, 27]. Right : non-prompt and prompt D^0 elliptic and triangular flow as a function of p_T in 3 different centrality bins measured by CMS [28].

78 In addition, CMS has been able to measure the elliptic and triangular flow for
 79 prompt and non-prompt D^0 mesons in Pb-Pb collisions [28]. The results are shown
 80 in Figure 4 right as a function of p_T . The v_2 of non-prompt D^0 is significantly
 81 lower the prompt D^0 v_2 at low p_T , and this difference becomes more pronounced
 82 in peripheral collisions where v_2 is large. The flow is also shifted to higher p_T with in-
 83 creasing mass, indicating a possible incomplete thermalization of the beauty quark.
 84 The measurements also suggest an increase of v_2 towards peripheral collisions, sim-
 85 ilar to light hadrons, a further indication that flow is a consequence of initial space
 86 anisotropy.

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In figure 5, the measurement of the B_c^+ R_{AA} by CMS [29] in Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV is presented. This measurement is particularly interesting as the B_c^+ is a unique charm-bottom state, sensitive both to the energy loss and the recombination, in an intermediate situation between the charmonium and bottomonium states. The R_{AA} shows a moderate suppression at high p_T , and a hint of an enhancement at low p_T . Compared with other heavy mesons, the suppression is less important for the B_c^+ , hinting that the recombination processes might be an important component of B_c^+ production.

Figure 5: B_c^+ R_{AA} in Pb–Pb collisions measured by CMS [29] compared with other mesons (left) and quarkonia (right).

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Looking at the jets from b allows to investigate heavy flavor production in a higher p_T range. Figure 6 presents the R_{AA} of b -jets measured by ATLAS [30] in Pb–Pb collisions at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 5.02$ TeV as a function of p_T , compared to the one of inclusive jets. In central collisions the R_{AA} values for the b -jets are higher than for inclusive jets. This could be explained by the influence of b -jet fragmentation and/or of the mass on parton energy loss.

Figure 6: Raa of the b jets as a function of p_T measured with ATLAS [30] in 3 different centrality bins compared with models [13, 31].

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The measurement of heavy flavor mesons and baryons production can also be used to evaluate the fragmentation functions. In Figure 7 the measurement of the charm fragmentation functions by ALICE [32] in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV is presented, compared to the results obtained in e^+e^- and ep collisions. An increase of the Λ_c^+ production is observed, accompanied by a concomitant decrease in the D^0 production. This shows that universality, i.e. the independence with respect to the collision system, of the parton to hadron fragmentation is not valid.

A measurement of beauty fragmentation function has been performed by CMS [33] in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. Figure 7 shows the ratio of the B^0/B^+ fragmenta-

Figure 7: Left : Charm quark fragmentation function measured with ALICE [32]. Middle : B^0/B^+ ratio as a function of p_T measured in CMS [33] Right : B_s^+/B^+ ratio as a function of p_T measured in CMS [33] and LHCb [34].

tion functions and the ratio B_s^+/B^+ . The former is compatible with one and shows no p_T or rapidity dependence, which is expected from strong isospin symmetry. The latter decreases with increasing p_T and then is flat for $p_T > 18 \text{ GeV}/c$, and shows no rapidity dependence. The p_T trend is compatible in the overlapping region with the measurement performed by LHCb at forward rapidity [34].

Finally, ALICE and CMS have measured the baryon to meson ratio for light and heavy flavor for different multiplicity classes in pp collisions [36] and p-Pb collisions [37] respectively. The results are presented in Figure 8 as a function p_T . Whereas in ALICE, the Λ/K_s^0 and Λ_c^+/D^0 ratio show a similar trend as function of multiplicity, with the peak shifting towards higher p_T with increasing multiplicity in both cases, indicating that there is a potential common mechanism for light valence quark- and charm-baryon formation, in CMS the ratios of light and heavy flavour baryon-to-meson show different behaviors, the heavy flavor baryon-to-meson ratio showing no discernible trend with increasing multiplicity, contrary to the Λ/K_s^0 ratio.

Figure 8: Baryon to meson ratio as a function of p_T for different multiplicity classes measured in ALICE [36] in pp collisions at 13 TeV (left) and in CMS [37] in p-Pb collisions at 8.16 TeV .

In conclusion, The ability to measure several observables provides a solid base for model comparison and improves our understanding of heavy quark interaction with the medium. However more precise measurements and models are needed to differentiate between different scenarios. With the Run3 data, more precise measurements will be possible with smaller uncertainties, improving our understanding of heavy flavor production

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